

A note on the stoichiometric mechanism for ligand replacement reactions of square-planar complexes of platinum(II)[†]

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Abstract : Based on available evidence in literature, particularly insensitivity of the rate on the overall charge on the complex, ligand replacement reactions of square-planar complexes of platinum(II) are best regarded as interchange (*I*) process in which bond formation and bond dissociation make comparable contributions in generating the transition state. But for isoelectronic gold(III) the reactions are associative (*A*).

Accumulated data in literature^{1,2} on such reactions of square-planar complexes of metals in general are accounted for by a bimolecular displacement process, and following the nomenclature introduced by Langford and Gray³, the mechanism is considered associative, *A* process. This is usually represented as shown below :

The nucleophile Y is solvent (S) for the solvent-dependent path of the two-term rate-law (see below) usually observed in donor solvents. In this case, from the initial product MA₃S the S is displaced by Y in a fast step forming the final product MA₃Y.

However, in cases of complexes of platinum(II), where the rates of such reactions are insensitive to the overall charge on the complexes^{4,5}, this simple assignment is not adequate and the behaviour is more in keeping with an

interchange process (*I*) in which both bond formation and bond dissociation make comparable contributions in generating the transition state. Accordingly, the reaction scheme proposed in one of the earliest studies of such reactions⁴ is much more appropriate and can be represented schematically in a simplified form as shown below. In this it was logically assumed (for which there is now evidence⁶) that in solution in a good donor solvent the square-planar complex will have two weakly bonded solvent molecules in the axial positions, which may exist in equilibrium with a species having another nucleophile (present in the solution) weakly bonded to the metal in place of a solvent molecule. In the rate-determining step of the displacement process, as the bond to the departing nucleophile breaks there is concurrent bond formation by the two weakly bonded axial nucleophiles :

[†]Dedicated in memory of Sir P. C. Ray on the occasion of his 154th birth anniversary.

In addition to accounting for the two-term rate-law, which is generally observed for such reactions of square-planar complexes, viz.,

$$\text{Rate} = \{k_S + k_Y[Y]\} [\text{PtA}_3\text{X}]$$

this also accounts for the fact that the values of the volume of activation for both k_S and k_Y paths for reactions of complexes of platinum(II) are significantly negative⁷⁻¹¹, but generally less so for the k_Y path^{8,11}, being *ca.* -18 to -15 cm³ mol⁻¹ for k_S and *ca.* -12 to -6 cm³ mol⁻¹ for k_Y ¹². The smaller negative value in the latter case arises from a positive contribution due to desolvation of the weakly bonded axial Y as it gets normally bonded to the Pt.

It is worth noting that Gronig *et al.*¹³ interpreted the results of their observations on the reaction of $\text{Pt}(\text{OH}_2)_4^{2+}$ with L forming $\text{PtL}(\text{OH}_2)_3^{n+}$ as interchange process with a gradual change of mechanism from I_d for L = H₂O, DMSO (n = 2) to I_a for L = Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, SCN⁻ (n = 1).

For reactions of complexes of isoelectronic Au(III) experimental evidences suggest associative A mechanism¹⁴.

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